

Various roles of ehretia laevis roxb: A review article

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Abstract- Historically, the uncommon Indian medicinal herb ehretia laevis has been employed. Various products made from the plant include decorations, pot herbs, wood and stone dye, medications, wines, and cosmetics. There is a huge opportunity for the discovery of new drugs to treat human health issues because the plant kingdom has not been sufficiently investigated for its medicinal potential. In the Indian state of Maharashtra, ehretia laevis roxb. has historically been applied locally to treat wounds and manage pain. Pharmacological research has proven that the genus's raw extracts or specific compounds have anti-snake venom, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, anti-arthritis, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. An objective of this review paper is to know more about the plant ehretia laevis roxb for the further study of research in Cosmetics.

Key words: Ehretia laevis roxb, therapeutic action, medical action.

I. INTRODUCTION

The invention and mass production of chemically synthesized medicines has revolutionized health care in most parts of the world over the last 100 years. Orthodox practitioners and herbal medicines are also used by significant segments of the population in developing countries for primary care. Herbal medicine is one of the most important branches of herbal medicine worldwide. In developing countries like India, the bulk of the world's population also relies on herbal medicines to fulfil their health needs [1]. According to the World Health Organization, 80 percent of people use natural medicines for any aspect of their primary health care, exposing them to lesser-known side effects and dangers associated with chemically synthesized pharmacological drugs. As a result, bioactive extracts of medicinal plants, as well as their herbal medicine formulations, are a viable alternative to chemically synthesized medicines [2]. Indian medicinal plants are a promising field for treatment of several diseases. Ayurveda and Siddha practices originated in India and are still widely used among the Indian population. In addition, identification of Phyto-components of medicinal plants may be helpful for alleviate the infection. Hence, Indian medicinal plants can be considered as new option for their role to overcome viral transmission [3].

In present day's human civilization, the most used, acceptable and recognized form of medicine is plant derived medicinal products throughout the world. Plant generates several types of secondary metabolites that are biosynthetically produced from primary metabolites and these phytochemicals are the primary sources of herbal, pharmaceutical and nutraceutical formulations [4]. Other than providing construction material and food, plants supply active molecules of high value for pharmaceutical and cosmetic use through their metabolic machinery [5].

This genus' plants have medicinal value and are used in herbal medicine to treat diarrhea, cough, cachexia, syphilis, toothache, stomach and venereal diseases, as well as an antidote to vegetable poisoning (The wealth of India raw materials 1952). The E. laevis plant is used for a variety of medicinal purposes. The fresh root decoction is used to treat syphilis, and the stem bark decoction is used to treat diphtheria. Externally, tender leaf paste is used to treat eczema, and the powdered flowers mixed with milk are used as an aphrodisiac. The plant is used for a variety of purposes, including ornaments, pot herbs, wood and stone dye, medicines, wines, and cosmetics. In periods of shortage, the tree's inner bark and fruit are consumed.

I. Plant description

Ehretia laevis is a rare Indian medicinal plant used from the ancient period, it belonging to a member of the Boraginaceae or Borage family, and is native to India, Pakistan, Laos, Myanmar, Vietnam, China, and Bhutan. The Ehretia laevis Roxb. Is high valued medicinal plant and becoming rare in the state of Maharashtra. It has religious importance among Hindus. It is growing luxuriantly at Alandi near the Dnyaneshwar temple. The use of medicinal plants is increasing worldwide. The general information of Erthia laevis given below [6,7].

Fig 1: *Ehretia laevis* Roxb.

Kingdom: Plantae
 Division: Tracheophyta
 Class: Magnoliopsida
 Order: Boraginales
 Family: Boraginaceae
 Genus: *Ehretia*
 Species: *Ehretia laevis* (Roxb)
 Botanical name: *Ehretia laevis* Roxb.
 Synonyms: *Ehretia laevis* Var. *platyphylla* Merrill.
 Common/Local Name: Khanduchakka. Regional and Other Names:
 English: *Ehretia*,
 Gujarati: Vadhavaradi,
 Hindi: Bhairi, Chamror, Datranga, Tamoriya
 Nepali: Datingal Konkan: Kalo Gamdo
 Marathi: Ajaanvruksha, Datrang
 Tamil: Kuruviccai, Kalvirasu
 Telugu: Tellajuvvi, Paldattam Malayalam: Harandi Sanskrit: Charmavriksha
 Plant Family: Boraginaceae (borage)
 Habit and Habitat: Small deciduous tree, with short stem and grey bark, occasionally common.
 Native: India, China, Bhutan, Pakistan, Laos, Myanmar.

The plant has many such chemicals which are useful in malignancy, obesity, blood sugar, cardiovascular diseases, blood pressure, and lipids, and muscle wasting to minimize the risk of viral infection because maximum death in COVID-19 is associated with secondary complications. The plant has the property to fight infections of fungus and bacteria which may associate with viral infections [8]. This herbal plant has chemicals that have a very good effect on neural diseases like brain ischemia, and useful for the promotion of neural crest cell survival, sedative, anticonvulsant, anti-Alzheimer, Antiseizure, antidepressant, stroke [9]. The plant has thyroid uptake promotion property which will be useful for thyroid patients. Anticoagulant, the antiplatelet property is useful in old age patients and bedridden patients, also this will reduce the risk in heart patients. Beneficial chemicals to treat the peptic ulcer and cataract are available in this plant. This will help with the prevention of diseases [10].

II. High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC) Screening of *Ehretia Laevis* Roxb:

The selected plant *Ehretia laevis* have shown presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, Saponins, triterpenoids and steroids which are confirmed by HPTLC analysis.

Alkaloids- After Derivatization with Dragendorff's reagent, brown or orange-ish brown colour bands are observed in Alkaloids.

Flavonoids- After derivatization with Natural product reagent fluorescent bands are observed in Flavonoid compounds. As Fluorescent bands were observed it was concluded that Flavonoids are present.

Phenols- Phenols give Violish Blue band after derivatising in Alkali- Silica Reaction.

Glycoside- Glycosides show positive colour as bottle green bands after derivatising in Alcoholic KOH we can see a band with positive colour.

Saponins- Saponins give pinkish, greenish band after derivatising in ASR.

Steroids - Violet bands were observed in the given sample after derivatization with Anisaldehyde Sulphuric acid Reagent (ASR). Hence it can be concluded that Steroids are present.

Tannins- Tannins shows Black colored band after derivatising in Alcoholic FeCl₃.

Triterpenoids- Triterpenoids shows bluish and violet band after derivatising in ASR [11].

III. Wound Healing Property:

The inner bark of *Ehretia laevis* Roxb is used as food. Leaves are applied to ulcers and in headache. Fruit is astringent, anthelmintic, diuretic, demulcent, expectorant and used in affections of urinary passages, infections of lungs and spleen. Decoction of the fresh root is used in the treatment of syphilis and that of the stem bark for the treatment of diphtheria. The paste of tender leaves is used externally to cure eczema, and the powder of flowers with milk is employed as an aphrodisiac. Powdered kernel mixed with oil is a therapy in ringworm [12]

The study concluded that wound healing property of chloroform fraction of ethanol extract of *E. laevis* shows effective wound healing property like Povidon Iodine ointment in animal model [13]. Headache, skin conditions, and ulcers are treated with leaf juice. Venereal illness treated with root. In addition to being consumed, bark from *E. laevis* is also used as a gargle to treat throat infections. Fruits used to treat spleen, lung, and urinary tract infections. Excellent antibacterial action on both gram positive and gram negative bacteria is present in methanolic leaf extract. Treatment with leaf extract promotes anti-arthritic action. Using multiwalled carbon nanotube paste electrodes for electrochemical testing, it also demonstrates the promise of anti-diabetes drugs [14].

IV. Case Studies:

Ehretia laevis Roxb. plant is a being used for various ailments traditionally. It is commonly used for pain relief, wound healing and minor fractures.

Patient was suffering from severe pain in right shoulder with restricted movement of right shoulder from 8 days. Patient was assessed by (SPADI) Shoulder Pain & Disability Index. *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. leaves powder capsules were made up of 250 mg. Patient was advised to take two capsules in morning and two capsules at night after food. Daily 1 gm powder was administered internally for 7 days

Result- Internal use of *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. leaves powder is tested first time in this study for pain management in shoulder pain and assessed by (SPADI) Shoulder Pain & Disability Index And found very effective without any untoward side effects [15].

Patient having swelling, redness at right foot, yellowish pus discharge, blackness of skin and presence of ulcer for three years with severe pain and inability to perform his regular duties. *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. leaves paste was prepared under all aseptic precaution and daily dressing of *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. paste done on wound.

Result- Application of *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. reduce swelling as it has anti-inflammatory property and helps for proper supply of required nutrition. As swelling and pain is reduced by application of *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. leaves paste patient has got relief from insomnia and irritation within three days [16].

V. Antimicrobial Effect:

Antimicrobial activity of Crude and water extract of Khandu Chakka of was found to be better in *S. aureus* as compared to *E. coli*. Antimicrobial activity of Crude and Water extract of Khandu Chakka was found to better on *S. aureus* as compared to ethanolic extract. No antimicrobial activity was found in Ethanolic extract on *E. coli*.

Anti-microbial activity of water extract of Khandu Chakka was found to be best amongst three extracts. This study has generated evidence for anti-microbial activity, which will provide cost effective option for treating the wound infection [17].

The leaves of *ehretia laevis* have proven to be an optimum source of antimicrobial activity. Dental caries and root canal infections being polymicrobial in nature, can be delayed in their process via using a susceptible antimicrobial agent which acts against specific bacteria respectively. Though, Chlorhexidine is used as standard antimicrobial drugs for such use and hurdling the carious process, medicinal plants like *ehretia laevis* due to their herbal properties have the dual action of having fewer side effects actively pronounced by the chemical agents which are the prime ingredients of chlorhexidine as well as being an effective antimicrobial product [18].

The demonstration of antimicrobial bacterial activity against both gram positive and gram-negative bacteria may be indicative of the presence of broad-spectrum antibiotic compounds. All extract has shown excellent antibacterial activity against gram negative and gram-positive organism. When compared to chloroform, methanol and aqueous methanolic extract showed the high antibacterial activity on gram positive and gram-negative bacteria and aqueous extracts shows the high antibacterial activity on gram negative than gram positive [19].

VI. Blood Coagulation Property:

The reduction in coagulation time of plasma and blood may be due presence of some blood coagulating compounds in *Ehretia laevis* extracts. Chung KT et al (1998) reported that presence of tannic acid in khandu chakka accelerates blood clotting [20].

VII. Antiarthritic activity

Arthritis is an inflammatory disorder involving damage of joints. There are over a hundred different forms of arthritis, of which rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, and psoriatic arthritis are the most common. The treatment of any systemic

disorder with allopathic drugs causes moderate-to-severe adverse effect that could cause death. Hence, alternative systems of medicine are being explored to treat diseases. *E. laevis* treatment supports antiarthritic activity. Of the three parts such as stem, leaf, and bark and fruit employed, the leaf extract was the most effective. This antiarthritic response may be due to the presence of active constituents such as hexadecanoic acid (palmitic acid), oleanenic acid, and other fixed oils [21].

VIII. Potential herbal remedy for mouth microflora:

The antimicrobial sensitivity data exhibit the efficacy of *E. laevis* leaf extracts against isolated and selected oral microflora i.e., *Streptococcus* spp, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida* spp. This folklore herb *E. laevis* has great potential as an alternative antibacterial and antifungal drug. Nowadays, the problem of drug resistance in *S. aureus* and *Candida* spp is increasing. So, it can be an alternative therapeutic agent for the oral antimicrobial treatment or control of oral microflora. Therefore, it can be a good source for pharmaceutical drug formulation research, and for the preparation of herbal products such as oral ointments, mouthwash and toothpaste [22].

IX. Nanoparticles of *Ehretia laevis* Roxb:

Silver nanoparticles were synthesized from *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. leaf extract by one-step green synthesis method. The nanoparticles were crystalline in nature, spherical shaped with 25 to 35 nm diameter.

The nanoparticles were highly stable in solution and active in nature. It possessed biological activities like cytotoxicity, larvicidal activity, and antimicrobial activity in some extent. The synthesized nanoparticles presented photocatalytic activity in presence of light. The kinetic model for methylene blue degradation in presence of nanoparticles and light was established at pseudo second order kinetics. The nanoparticles were synthesized by green synthesis method which made them inexpensive and less hazardous [23].

X. Discussion:

The plant *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. has historically been used to treat a variety of illnesses. It is frequently applied to treat small fractures, wounds, and pain. Additionally, using this herbal plant to treat pain would lessen the negative effects of contemporary medications like non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

Leaves are used to treat headaches and ulcers. Fruit is used as an expectorant, anthelmintic, diuretic, demulcent, and in the treatment of lung and spleen disorders as well as conditions affecting the urinary tract. A natural anthelmintic, seeds.

The leaves' methanolic extract, which is useful for treating arthritis. Silver nanoparticles were also manufactured using a one-step green synthesis process from *Ehretia laevis* Roxb. leaf extract. Antimicrobial, larvicidal, and cytotoxic action was demonstrated by the nanoparticles.

The present study suggested that all the solvents extract of *E. laevis* leaves have a great potential as antimicrobial agents against selected oral pathogens, and they can be used as an alternative medicine in the treatment or control of oral bacterial as well as fungal oral microflora which are mostly cause the dental infections.

XI. Conclusion

These medical properties of the plant will pave the way for additional research and will create good chances for employment and farming, helping to enhance the global economy. This spiritual plant has the potential to pave the road for humanity.

As demonstrated, the plant has numerous applications. The plant's research and application have broad implications in both the medical and cosmetic fields.

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